

Data Stewardship

Federated repositories

a. Architecture of the solution

Master:

ubuntu-18.04.2-live-server-amd64

dspace-6.3

Running in a Oracle VM Virtualbox

Slave1:

ubuntu-18.04.2-live-server-amd64

dspace-6.3

Running in a Oracle VM Virtualbox

Slave2:

CentOS7

dataverse-4.15

Running in a VMware Workstation Player

b. Steps performed to implement the solution (everything that would help you or your colleagues replicate your experiment)

DSpace

First of all we need a virtual machine with ubuntu-18.04.2-live-server. There are a lot of manuals out there, basically you just have to download the ISO-File and set it up with Oracle VM Virtualbox Manager.

To install dspace, we recommend following manual. Nearly all install guides are out of date and not working anymore because of a maven update or something else.

<https://listechsavvy.blogspot.com/2017/12/installation-of-dspace-62-on-ubuntu-1604.html>

There is only one step missing. You have to change the default java version because the new one is not working with dspace. Use the following command and change to java 1.8:

```
sudo update-alternatives --config java
```

After following the steps of the manual, you can access dspace repository with

[http://\[yourIpAddress\]:8080/xmlui/](http://[yourIpAddress]:8080/xmlui/)

To change the look of the xmlui page, we need to configure the css file in

```
/opt/tomcat/webapps/xmlui/themes/Mirage/lib/css/style.css
```

To change the Title we modify

```
/opt/tomcat/webapps/xmlui/i18n/messages.xml
```

Dspace - Slave - OAI:

To import the created metadata to the oai context, we need to execute this:
`sudo /dspace/bin/dspace oai import -c`

Check the OAI with [http://\[yourIpAddress\]:8080/oai/](http://[yourIpAddress]:8080/oai/)

After the metadata is imported you can use the identifier from another repository to harvest the metadata.

Response Date 2019-06-28 14:12:01

List of Sets

Results fetched 5

Ethnomusicology [com_123456789_1]	Records Identifiers
Audio-Files [col_123456789_4]	Records Identifiers
Documents [col_123456789_2]	Records Identifiers

Dspace - Master - OAI:

To harvest metadata from other repositories we can use the XMLUI. Create a collection, edit it and go to data source options. User your OAI-Provider address. Optionally its possible to use a OAI Set ID to harvest a specific part of the metadata.

Bearbeiten der Sammlung: Dspace Repo - Ethnomusicology Metadata

Metadaten bearbeiten | Bearbeiterrollen zuordnen | **Quelle des Inhalts** | Pflegen

Quelle des Inhalts:
 Dies ist eine Standard-DSpace-Sammlung Diese Sammlung bezieht ihren Inhalt via Harvesting aus einer externen Quelle.

Die per Harvesting bearbeitete Sammlung
OAI Provider:
http://10.0.0.12:8080/oai/request

OAI Set ID:
com_123456789_1

Metadatenformat:
Simple Dublin Core

Inhalt wird über Harvesting bezogen:
HNur die Metadaten über Harvesting beziehen.

Ergebnisse des letzten Harvesting:
Harvest from http://10.0.0.12:8080/oai/request successful on 2019-06-23 22:45:55.788

Aktueller Harvesting-Status:
Sammlung fürs Harvesting bereit

[Einstellungen ändern](#) [Jetzt importieren](#) [Den Status zurücksetzen und die Sammlung nochmal importieren](#)

[Speichern](#) [Zurück](#)

To harvest metadata from an external source, just search for a provider and use the address (<https://transactions.ismir.net/jms/index.php/up/oai>):

Metadaten bearbeiten Bearbeiterrollen zuordnen **Quelle des Inhalts** Pflegen

Quelle des Inhalts:
 Dies ist eine Standard-DSpace-Sammlung Diese Sammlung bezieht ihren Inhalt via Harvesting aus einer externen Quelle.

Die per Harvesting bearbeitete Sammlung
OAI Provider:
<https://transactions.ismir.net/jms/index.php/up/oai>

OAI Set ID:
all

Metadatenformat:
Simple Dublin Core

Inhalt wird über Harvesting bezogen:
HNur die Metadaten über Harvesting beziehen.

Ergebnisse des letzten Harvesting:
Harvest from <https://transactions.ismir.net/jms/index.php/up/oai> successful on 2019-06-23 22:59:23.622

Aktueller Harvesting-Status:
Sammlung fürs Harvesting bereit

[Einstellungen ändern](#) [Jetzt importieren](#) [Den Status zurücksetzen und die Sammlung nochmal importieren](#)

[Speichern](#) [Zurück](#)

With “Import now” the metadata is collected and saved in the Master-Repository. In the system information menu, it is possible to use automatic harvesting of metadata.

Dspace Embargo:

To use embargo, we need to activate the submission process in the config folder:

[dspace]/config/item-submission.xml

Use following manual:

<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC6x/Embargo>

Now we can use embargo settings when uploading a file.

Dokument veröffentlichen

Beschreiben → Beschreiben → **Zugriffsrechte** → Hochladen → Überprüfen → DSpace Lizenz → Fertig

Zugriffsberechtigungen

Dokument im privaten Modus:

Wenn ausgewählt, ist das Dokument nicht suchbar.

Private

Embargo

Zugriff bis zu einem bestimmten Datum unter Embargo.:

Zulässige Formate: yyyy, yyyy-mm, yyyy-mm-tt

Begründung:

The reason for the embargo, typically for internal use only. Optional.

< Zurück Speicher / Abbrechen Weiter >

Dspace - Authenticate with ORCID ID

We can use following manual to activate ORCID authentication:

<https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC5x/ORCID+Integration>

```
plugin.named.org.dspace.content.authority.ChoiceAuthority = \  
org.dspace.content.authority.SolrAuthority = SolrAuthority
```

The feature relies on the following configuration parameters in `dspace.cfg`. To activate the default settings it suffices to remove the comment hashes (“#”) for the following lines. See the section at the bottom of this page what these parameters mean exactly and how you can tweak the configuration.

```
solr.authority.server=${solr.server}/authority  
choices.plugin.dc.contributor.author = SolrAuthority  
choices.presentation.dc.contributor.author = authorLookup  
authority.controlled.dc.contributor.author = true  
authority.author.indexer.field.1=dc.contributor.author
```

The final part of configuration is to add the authority consumer in front of the list of event consumers. Add “authority” in front of the list as displayed below.

```
event.dispatcher.default.consumers = authority, versioning, discovery, eperson, harvester
```

We need to modify the `dspace.cfg` file like described on the link and load the index with `[dspace]/bin/dspace index-authority`

Dataverse

In the first step we also tried to set up the repository on a Ubuntu system. However, after a few failed tries we gave up on this system and decided to switch to CentOS, as this is also what Dataverse recommends.

For Dataverse to work a lengthy list of prerequisites has to be installed:

<http://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/installation/prerequisites.html>

On top of the installation, almost all of these requirements have to be manually configured by changing config files. In many cases the documentation is really not enough to get this done, as it sometimes just instructs to change file_xy.config, however there is no information given where the file is located. This is even further complicated by the fact that also system files have to be adapted, so sometimes it is not even clear if the file to change is of the software that was just installed, or a system file.

After all the prerequisites are installed (which will take several hours, with configuration - as almost nothing just works out of the box) one can finally install Dataverse. In our case however this failed, as the install script could not access PostgreSQL. From there we went on to troubleshoot this problem: First we checked that the configurations and access levels were actually set to the ones that were specified in the documentation - this was correct. Next we went on to several other measures that we found online.

None of this worked.

The weird thing is that PGSQL is running, but still the installation script cant access it:

```
Last login: Sun Jun 30 04:21:13 EDT 2019 on pts/2
[root@project-open-v50 ~]# /usr/bin/systemctl start postgresql-9.6
[root@project-open-v50 ~]# /usr/bin/systemctl status postgresql-9.6
● postgresql-9.6.service - PostgreSQL 9.6 database server
   Loaded: loaded (/usr/lib/systemd/system/postgresql-9.6.service; enabled; vendor preset: disabled)
   Active: active (running) since Sun 2019-06-30 05:17:00 EDT; 1min 26s ago
     Docs: https://www.postgresql.org/docs/9.6/static/
   Process: 1204 ExecStartPre=/usr/pgsqli-9.6/bin/postgresql96-check-db-dir ${PGDATA} (code=exited, status=0/SUCCESS)
  Main PID: 1231 (postmaster)
   CGroup: /system.slice/postgresql-9.6.service
           └─1231 /usr/pgsqli-9.6/bin/postmaster -D /var/lib/pgsqli/9.6/data/
             └─1282 postgres: logger process
               └─1310 postgres: checkpointer process
                 └─1311 postgres: writer process
                   └─1312 postgres: wal writer process
                     └─1313 postgres: autovacuum launcher process
                       └─1314 postgres: stats collector process
```

```
Found Postgres psql command, version 9.6.14.
(Using psql version 9.6: /bin/psql)
Checking if we can talk to Postgres as the admin user...
(Tried executing: PGPASSWORD=secret; export PGPASSWORD; /bin/psql -h 127.0.0.1 -p 5432 -U postgres -d po
stgres -c 'SELECT * FROM pg_roles' > /dev/null 2>&1)
Nope, I haven't been able to connect to the local instance of PostgreSQL as the admin user.

Is postgresql running?
On a RedHat-like system, you can check the status of the daemon with

    service postgresql start

On MacOSX, use Applications -> PostgreSQL -> Start Server.
(or, if there's no "Start Server" item in your PostgreSQL folder,
simply restart your MacOSX system!)

Also, please make sure that the daemon is listening to network connections!
- at least on the localhost interface. (See "Installing Postgres" section
of the installation manual).

Finally, did you supply the correct admin password?
Don't know the admin password for your Postgres installation?
- then simply set the access level to "trust" temporarily (for localhost only!)
in your pg_hba.conf file. Again, please consult the
installation manual).
[root@project-open-v50 dvininstall]# █
```

We worked on this issue for several hours, but after multiple failed attempts gave up on this repository.

c. Links to the screencasts

i. Include description of what each demonstrates

- a) Upload of data to slaves and how closed access works (what is visible and for whom)

<https://youtu.be/zlO2Z94jQRs>

In this screencast we show how to upload data to a collection.

- b) Search and access to data on slaves (owner perspective)

<https://youtu.be/CpfgOTVFNcg>

In this screencast we access the data on our slave repository logged in as the owner of the data. We can view and edit our uploaded documents.

- c) Search and access to data on slaves (other users perspective)

<https://youtu.be/SSpP3PQ6Y18>

In this screencast we access the data on our slave repository logged in as a user of the data. We only see public metadata and can only access data for which we have the permission.

- d) Search and access to data on master

<https://youtu.be/YHO114sZelo>

In this screencast we are logged in to the master repository and search and access the metadata of our slave repository and from an external repository. Because we only harvest the metadata of the repositories, we have to go directly to the slave repository to download the data.

d. Discussion and comparison of repository systems used

i. Installation

Dspace

Installation of Dspace is very hard first, but after a few fails with old manuals and learning about the system it's not that bad at all. The admin needs good knowledge about linux systems and programming skills to change anything in the configurations of the server.

Dataverse

It took a few failed attempts for us before we finally gave in, as we were not able to set up dataverse. The main problems are the lengthy prerequisites that it needs to run - especially considering, that for almost every prerequisite installations also the config files have to be adapted. I think this could be improved drastically with little to no effort on the dataverse side by simply providing pre configured VMs that one can simply use. Or as another potential solutions they could provide a script that takes care of the full setup including prerequisite software - however, judging from our experience this would most likely not work, as every system behaves a little different with so many moving parts.

ii. Content organisation

Dspace

The content of dspace is organized in communities and collections. Collections are part of communities. The documents are saved in the collections. If the user wants content in multiple collection, it's possible to harvest the metadata or even the hole data from collections or communities. It's intuitive to use and the upload process is well defined. After some practise, the user is able to upload papers or other files very fast. One data upload can consist of multiple files.

Dataverse

[Judgement based on existing repositories]

The organization of content seems rather intuitive, which is a good thing. We could be biased here as we have already worked with a range of repositories, so maybe this makes is easier for us to get familiar with new repositories. Overall it is easy to find what one is looking for and the interaction with the results also works very natural.

iii. Metadata

Dspace

Dspace metadata is completely adjustable. The default metadata is already well defined. Multiple metadata namespaces can be created to use it for specific data topics. Multiple languages are supported, that means you can add the metadata in different languages and mark it with a language tag.

Dataverse

[Judgement based on documentation and existing repositories]

Changing the metadata is possible and quite straightforward. Special properties can be set for fields and it is also allowed to use special vocabularies.

In the webview the metadata is displayed in a structured way and hints are also provided for the fields so that users know what they mean.

iv. Content presentation

Dspace

The communities and collections gives the user a good oversight about the data in the repo. There is a structured view of data objects with the metadata, description and the files included. The files can be downloaded to view them.

Dataverse

[Judgement based on existing repositories]

The content is displayed in a very structured way. Everything that seems to us would be useful is included without the content looking overcrowded. The data is easy to cite and easy to download, which we believe are the most important aspects.

v. User management and access rights

Dspace

There are some plugins to manage the user login of Dspace repos. For example it is possible to authenticate with an ORCID but it has to be implemented to the system which is not very simple. The system administrator has to adjust the server configuration and maintain it to keep the data synchron.

The access rights can be set on all levels of data objects in the system for single users or user groups.

Dataverse

[Judgement based on documentation]

Identification with ORCID is possible, however special care has to be taken when installing the prerequisites for this to work.

User Management is built into the solution with options to see the users in table format or get information on them via an API.

Furthermore, standard actions like merging of accounts and changing their ID as well as sending out email to get confirmations of the users email address.

vi. Interoperability

Dspace

Dspace interoperability with external systems and databases: (from Dspace wiki)

- Scripts are provided to query periodically bibliographic databases such as: PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science
- Deduplications can be used to merge found records in multiple sources or previously entered.
- SOAP WebServices for READ-ONLY access to CRIS information
- DSpace-CRIS is more machine friendly than ever. It supports the following signposting patterns: Author, Identifier, Publication Boundary
- Integrated with bibliometric database (PubMed Central Cited by, Scopus and Web of Science)
- ORCID integration for both public and member APIs

With plugins, Dspace can be extended even more.

Dataverse

[Judgement based on documentation]

Dataverse provides a long list of APIs that make it very easy to include the repository into other applications. For example there are APIs that allow access to the data itself.

Furthermore, there is an API that can access the search, which could also be very handy when integrating dataverse with other applications.

Lastly there is also an OAI API that can be used for metadata harvesting as it was the goal of this exercise.

vii. Other (e.g. quality of documentation, community support, architecture, etc.)

Dspace

There is some community support for Dspace. The most problems while implementing the system were already mentioned in some way. There is a Dspace Wiki which is very accurately and gives a lot of information. It is only a little tricky with the different versions of Dspace. Some descriptions are completely different in newer versions.

Software versions are the biggest problem for the implementation because of problems with newer versions of java or other tools.

Dataverse

There is extensive documentation, however it is rather hard to use for novices. A few points were missing all together which we assume was the case mainly as it was written by people that are very familiar with the subject - but people that set something like this up for the first time might have major issues here. One example for this would be the missing paths to a lot of configuration files: If one has changes these already quite often it will come very natural to locate them, but for novices this will include a lot of googling and trial and error to find a solution for something that is actually trivial.

Furthermore it seems that parts of the documentation do not fit to the current version of software that has to be installed, as some of the config files had different properties than described in the documentation.

Lastly, there is almost no information to troubleshoot problems - if the installation works perfectly fine this might not be a problem, but once you run into issues this becomes a major downside. It took us a lot of googling and stackoverflow sites just to get the prerequisites up and running, as the steps in the documentation almost never worked without further actions. Dataverse depends on a large number of other software which I would judge as risky. Any one dependency has to be kept up to date while still continuing to work with the other components. One can already see in the documentation that these versions do not always work together smoothly:

Glassfish

Glassfish Version 4.1 is required. There are known issues with newer versions of the Glassfish 4.x series so it should be avoided. For details, see <https://github.com/IQSS/dataverse/issues/2628> . The issue we are using the track support for Glassfish 5 is <https://github.com/IQSS/dataverse/issues/4248> .